

DIGITAL INDIA: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

Ms. Deepa Mishra

Assistant Professor,

Department of Information Technology

Sahyog College of Management Studies, Thane

Introduction:

Government of India has planned and implemented many drives like Beti Bachao- Beti Padhao, Swachha Bharat, Make In India and many more for the welfare indian citizens and Digital of India is one of ongoing drive. Digital India was launched on 1st July 2015 by Prime Minister Shri. Narendra Modi. There were many objectives behind this Digital India

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drive like, to provide quality education to the students residing in rural areas, to provide quality health, to give real time global information to farmers, awareness of digital literacy, creating more job opportunities for the young generations of India, Making India digitally empowered country, connecting people of rural areas with high speed internet network, so that they can take advantages of all the government services which is available online. E-Governance also got introduced in this Digital India campaign. Objectives of e-governance is to bring transparency in the governing process, to get response from government on time and to reduce corruption in the government.

Population of India in 2020 is 138 Crore and India is the 2nd most populated country in the world. But despite of a population of 138 Crore only 55% people are using Internet. That means half of the population is still deprived of the internet. This statistics shows that still we are far away from the dream of becoming digitally empowered country in the field of technology. Most of the citizens are not aware of the Government policies and plans of digitalization.

Research Methodology:

This research paper is based on the secondary data analysis and the information is fetched from the internet via government websites, journals and research papers.

Objectives of the paper:

- To study the concept of Digital India campaign.
- To find out the Challenges faced in the execution of this campaign.
- To find out the opportunities.

9 pillars of Digital India:

Under Digital India programme, government is focusing initially on following 9 pillars which will help us to achieve the dream to Digital India into reality:

1. Broadband Highways: 2,50,000 village Panchayats would be covered under the National Optical Fibre Network (NOFN) by December 2016 and has achieved around 1,40,000 connections thus far. National Information Infrastructure (NII) would integrate the network and cloud infrastructure in the country to provide high-speed internet connectivity and cloud platform to various government departments up to the panchayat level.

2. Universal access to mobile connectivity: In India approximately 55,619 villages do not have mobile coverage. The aim is to provide mobile coverage for the exposed villages which will cost around 16,000 crore during 2014-2018.
3. Public Internet Access Programme: The two sub components of Public Internet Access Programme are Common Services Centres (CSCs) and Post Offices as multi-service centres. one CSC in each Gram Panchayat will be provided. CSCs- Common Services Centres would be made centres for delivery of government services and business services and a total of 150,000 Post Offices are suggested to be transformed into multi service centres for the rural area citizen.
4. Electronics Manufacturing: This pillar focuses on promoting electronics manufacturing in the country with the target of NET ZERO Imports by 2020 as a striking demonstration of intent.
5. Early Harvest Programmes: Cities with population of over 1 million and tourist centres would be provided with public wi-fi hotspots to promote digital cities. All books will be converted into e books. E-mail will be the primary mode of communication with the government. Bio-metric Attendance System will be installed in all central government offices so that tracking of attendance can be done smoothly. SMS based weather forecast information and disaster alerts would also be provided.
6. e-Governance – Reforming Government through Technology: Government Process Re-engineering using IT to simplify and make the government processes more efficient is critical for transformation to make the delivery of government services more effective across various government domains.
7. eKranti - Electronic delivery of services: The aim of eKranti is online delivery of services to people be it education, health, financial inclusion or justice.
8. Information for All: Government should interact with the citizen of India via social media and web based platform. MyGov.in is a platform for citizen's interaction with government, it has been launched by the Prime Minister on 26th July, 2014.
9. IT for Jobs: Providing training to the youth of country for availing employment opportunities in the IT/ITES sector is main objective of this pillar. Target is to train 1 Crore students from smaller town to villages to get jobs into IT Sectors.

Apps made under Digital India:

Under Digital India Campaign, the government launched a lot of applications for the public, so that the public can use the technologies, and become digital, and can take advantage of government services.

1. MyGov:

MyGov app is a platform for citizens found by government of India, where citizens can share their views and propose suggestions related to various issues and problems of society and the whole country.

2. UMANG:

UMANG-Unified Mobile Application for New-age Governance. This app is developed by the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology and National e-Governance Division and launched by prime minister on 23rd November 2017. This app helps you to access Pan Asian nation e-Gov services from the Central, State, native bodies and government agencies on the app, web, SMS and IVR channels. At present, 76 departments of 19 states 380 services are available on Umang App. Those services includes Aadhaar Seva, DigiLocker, AICTE, Bharat Bill Pay, Ayushman Bharat Yojna and many more.

3. PMO India:

This is an official App of the Indian Prime Minister's workplace. Through this app, you'll simply get updated by all the most recent info, news updates & alternative news associated with the Prime Minister's workplace.

4. BHIM – MAKING INDIA CASHLESS:

BHIM-Bharat Interface for money. This app is associate initiative to achieve quick, secure, convenient cashless payments on your smartphone. It's connected with a Unified Payment Interface (UPI) applications, named after B. R. Ambedkar and launched on 30th December 2016, to supply fast cash transfers online. This app is launched by the National Payment Corporation of India (NPCI) and it is a part of the Digital India campaign.

5. OnlineRTI – File RTI Online:

RTI – Right to Information Act. This app permits citizens of India to induce info from the govt. This act applies to all twenty nine states and seven union territories. RTI will facilitate to look out for any information associated with government office.

It conjointly helps to clear any personal work unfinished with administration. However you can request any info which will be a threat to national security. With the assistance of this app, you will be able to file associate RTI application directly from your Smartphone.

6. mAadhaar :

mAadhaar app is launched by Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI). Its motive is to give a platform to citizen of India to get information in the smartphone associated with their Aadhar card like Name, Date of Birth, Gender & Address along a photograph that is joined with their Aadhaar number in smartphones.

7. mPassportSeva:

Smt. Sushma Swaraj launched the mPassportSeva Mobile App on 26th June 2018. The main motive behind this project is to provide all Passport-related services to Indian Citizens in a quick, efficient and transparent manner.

8. DigiLocker:

DigiLocker is a secure app developed by the Ministry of Electronics & Information Technology. Any one can store or save all the important documents in the locker like PAN Card, Driving License, passport, mark sheets etc. with them anytime anywhere and can access it any moment of time whenever required, without carrying the hardcopy of such documents.

Challenges:

1. Digital illiteracy ratio is high in rural area as most of the citizens are not aware of the Government policies and plans of digitalization and are still far away from the use of technology due to lack of knowledge of digital literacy and this is main challenge for the government to implement Digital India campaign successfully.
2. India has over 1000 languages and dialects. Non availability of digital services in local languages is also a roadblock in digital literacy.
3. Due to low Internet speed in rural areas they cannot use the government services which is available online.
4. Lack of skilled staffs in the field of technology.
5. Poor infrastructure. A few challenges are confronted within the rollout of broadband systems in rustic zones. These emerge due to a comparatively lower level of foundation accessible in provincial zones than in urban regions.
6. Lack of coordination among the departments.

7. Over 70 per cent of rural India do not have access to the internet. Broadband penetration in provincial zones is limited to a mere 29.2 per cent, as on 31 March 2020. Bihar-21.69, Uttar Pradesh-21.64, Jammu & Kashmir-16.58, Madhya Pradesh -23.88, and West Bengal -25 are the states that have the slightest number of web supporters per 100 people.
8. Terror of cyber-crime and breach of security has been obstacle in adoption of technology. These are the challenges proving roadblock for the aim of Digital India which need to resolve.

Advantages:

1. Digital India points at giving more internet connectivity and more access to information so that individuals can be benefitted with the government services.
2. Citizens can file grievance online, book tickets online, go through the feedbacks of other tourists which will help them finding nice tourist spot with better hotels.
3. Indian farmers can get real time information related to their crops and also they can post their products and attract more buyers which will spare their time and money. They can get way better benefits than normal.
4. Prime minister dreamt quality education for rural area students and using the internet available on high ways instructor as well as student can learn about different technologies and also can research on any topic.
5. Citizen having good internet connectivity can get access of government services like Income Tax Filling, Pan Card application, Submission of electricity Bill, Mobile recharge, Passport Seva etc. It'll make their lives simpler and uncomplicated.

Conclusion:

The Digital India program is now in the sixth year of its existence and several projects under the program have moved from the planning phase to the implementation phase. The project has started showing its impact on the lives of citizens and on businesses too. Several schemes of the project have been adopted successfully. The service like DigiLocker is now being used by over eight million users and have uploaded 430,324 documents. However the dream of Digital India is still far away as few of the nine pillars of Digital India mission are facing challenges in execution. Government need to give equal attention to each and every pillar so that this does not end up in failure and also everyone should be ready to adapt the challenges if comes in future then only prime minister's dream of Digital India will turn into reality.

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